

Multimodality Imaging Based Treatment Volume Definition for Reirradiation of Recurrent Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC)

Omer Sager*, Selcuk Demiral, Ferrat Dincoglan and Murat Beyzadeoglu

Department of Radiation Oncology;
University of Health Sciences, Ankara,
Turkey

Abstract

Objective: Small cell lung cancer (SCLC) may be considered as a major health concern as a leading cause of cancer related mortality worldwide. Despite intensive management, SCLC may follow an aggressive disease course with recurrent and/or metastatic disease in a considerable proportion of the patients. Herein, we assess multimodality imaging based treatment volume definition for reirradiation of recurrent SCLC.

Literature Review: Definition of treatment volume by multimodality imaging with incorporation of positron emission tomography (PET) or by computed tomography (CT)-simulation images only has been evaluated with comparative analysis for patients reirradiated for recurrent SCLC.

Results: A multidisciplinary team of experts from surgery, medical oncology, radiation oncology, and pulmonology has been involved in individualized patient evaluation. Decision making for reirradiation of patients with recurrent SCLC has been performed after comprehensive assessment considering the lesion size, localization and association with critical structures, previously administered treatments at initial diagnosis, and time interval from initial RT. Treatment volume determination by CT-only imaging and by CT-PET fusion based imaging has been assessed with comparative analysis. Ground truth target volume has been found to be identical with treatment volume determination by CT-PET fusion based imaging as the primary result of this study.

Conclusion: Incorporation of PET in RT planning process may be considered for patients receiving reirradiation for recurrent SCLC. Clearly, further investigation is required to shed light on this issue.

Keywords: Cytotoxicity; VitaminsB; Amygdalin; HPLC; Chitosan; Nanoparticles

Corresponding author:

Omer Sager, University of Health Sciences, Department of Radiation Oncology, Gn. Tevfik Saglam Cad. 06018, Etlik, Turkey, Tel: +90 312 304 4683.

✉ omersager@gmail.com

Citation: Sager O, Demiral S, Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M (2021) Multimodality Imaging Based Treatment Volume Definition for Reirradiation of Recurrent Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC). Arch Can Res Vol.9 No.1:1.

Received: March 08, 2021; **Accepted:** March 24, 2021; **Published:** March 31, 2021

Introduction

Lung cancer is among the most common and deadliest of all cancers worldwide. A broad categorization of lung cancer includes Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC) and Non Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) as the major subtypes. Although SCLC constitutes a smaller proportion of all lung cancers compared to NSCLC, it is the most aggressive subtype with a typically worse prognosis. Within this context, SCLC may be considered as a major health concern as a leading cause of cancer related mortality worldwide. Median survival for SCLC is typically around 1 year, however, there is extensive effort for improving treatment outcomes with multidisciplinary management and contemporary therapeutic strategies [1-3]. Radiation therapy (RT) plays an integral role in multimodality management of SCLC [4-6]. Despite intensive

management, SCLC may follow an aggressive disease course with recurrent and/or metastatic disease in a considerable proportion of the patients. Delivery of high radiation doses for recurrent disease management may be limited due to primary radiotherapeutic management and excessive radiation induced toxicity may be a critical concern for reirradiation of recurrent SCLC. Nevertheless, reirradiation offers an important therapeutic option for management of recurrent SCLC [7]. Radiotherapeutic approaches have improved over the years with introduction of contemporary irradiation strategies, adaptive RT methods, automatic segmentation techniques, molecular imaging methods, stereotactic irradiation, and modernized treatment delivery techniques including Intensity Modulated Radiation Therapy (IMRT), Image Guided Radiation Therapy (IGRT), Adaptive Radiation Therapy (ART), Breathing Adapted Radiation

Therapy (BART) [8-44]. In the context of SCLC management, there has been progress with introduction of immunotherapeutic strategies and normal tissue sparing RT strategies [45]. However, improving the toxicity profile of radiation delivery remains to be a critical aspect of radiotherapeutic management particularly in the setting of reirradiation for SCLC. Herein, we assess multimodality imaging based treatment volume definition for reirradiation of recurrent SCLC.

Literature Review

In this original research article, definition of treatment volume by multimodality imaging with incorporation of positron emission tomography (PET) or by CT-simulation images only has been evaluated with comparative analysis for patients reirradiated for recurrent SCLC. Ground truth target volume used as the reference for actual treatment and comparison purposes has been meticulously outlined by the board certified radiation oncologists after comprehensive assessment, colleague peer review, collaboration, and ultimate consensus. Detailed evaluation has been performed on an individual basis regarding the lesion size, localization, symptomatology, comorbidities, performance status, previous therapies and time interval from initial RT, and contemplated outcomes of reirradiation. CT-simulator (GE Lightspeed RT, GE Healthcare, Chalfont St. Giles, UK) has been used for RT simulation for treatment planning at our tertiary referral institution. Planning CT images have been acquired and then sent to the delineation workstation (SimMD, GE, UK) for definition of treatment volumes and surrounding critical structures. Either CT-simulation images only or fused CT and PET images have been used for treatment volume definition for reirradiation. Adequate coverage of target volume with optimal normal tissue sparing has been prioritized in treatment planning. Treatment volume determination with CT only and with incorporation of CT-PET fusion has been evaluated with comparative analysis. Synergy (Elekta, UK) linear accelerator (LINAC) has been utilized for treatment delivery and IGRT techniques have been routinely incorporated in radiotherapeutic management of patients with recurrent SCLC.

Results and Discussion

A multidisciplinary team of experts from surgery, medical oncology, radiation oncology, and pulmonology has been involved in individualized patient evaluation. Decision making for reirradiation of patients with recurrent SCLC has been performed after comprehensive assessment considering the lesion size, localization and association with critical structures, previously administered treatments at initial diagnosis, and time interval from initial RT.

Available RT planning systems at our tertiary cancer center have been used for precise radiation treatment planning to improve the therapeutic ratio. Determination of ground truth target volume to be used for actual treatment and for comparative analysis has been performed by board certified radiation oncologists after detailed assessment, colleague peer review, collaboration, and ultimate consensus. Synergy (Elekta, UK) LINAC has been used

for reirradiation. Treatment volume determination by CT-only imaging and by CT-PET fusion based imaging has been assessed with comparative analysis. Ground truth target volume has been found to be identical with treatment volume determination by CT-PET fusion based imaging as the primary result of this study.

SCLC is the most aggressive type of lung cancer with grim prognosis. Despite multimodality management, a considerable proportion of patients suffer from metastatic disease or recurrent SCLC. Therapeutic options are limited in the setting of recurrent disease. High RT doses delivered as part of initial management may limit the prescription of high radiation doses in the recurrent disease setting. Adverse effects of RT constitute important concerns since critical organs may be exposed to high cumulative radiation doses. Within this context, improving the toxicity profile of reirradiation becomes an indispensable component of recurrent SCLC management.

RT planning for SCLC is mostly based on CT simulation of patients in the treatment position. CT is utilized for dose calculations and RT planning, however, supplementary data from molecular imaging may aid in precise treatment volume determination. There has been extensive effort for optimization of treatment volumes for SCLC to improve the therapeutic ratio [46-48]. A major challenge in radiotherapeutic management of recurrent SCLC stems from the high delivered doses as part of initial therapy. There is a typical requirement for limiting the reirradiation doses for avoidance of adverse radiation effects. Contemporary strategies such as radiosurgical applications under rigid stereotactic immobilization and image guidance may improve outcomes of reirradiation, however, precise treatment volume determination becomes more important in the context of stereotactic reirradiation due to higher doses of radiation typically delivered in a single or a few fractions. While definition of larger than actual treatment volumes may cause substantial exposure of normal tissues and subsequent adverse effects, definition of smaller than actual treatment volumes may lead to inadequate target coverage with consequent treatment failure. From this standpoint, optimization of treatment volume determination is an important aspect of reirradiation for recurrent SCLC. In this study, we addressed the role of molecular imaging for reirradiation of recurrent SCLC. Indeed, many studies have also addressed multimodality imaging for improved target definition for radiotherapeutic management of several tumors [49-71].

Conclusion

In conclusion, incorporation of PET in RT planning process may be considered for patients receiving reirradiation for recurrent SCLC. Within this context, our study supporting the role of multimodality imaging for target definition of recurrent SCLC may add to the existing literature. Clearly, further investigation is required to shed light on this issue.

References

1. Dayen C, Debieuvre D, Molinier O, Raffy O, Paganin F, et al. (2017) New insights into stage and prognosis in small cell lung cancer: an analysis of 968 cases. *J Thorac Dis* 9: 5101-5111.

2. Lattuca-Truc M, Timsit JF, Levra MG, Ruckly S, Villa J, et al. (2019) Trends in response rate and survival in small-cell lung cancer patients between 1997 and 2017. *Lung Cancer* 131: 122-127.
3. Zhong L, Suo J, Wang Y, Han J, Zhou H, et al. (2020) Prognosis of limited-stage small cell lung cancer with comprehensive treatment including radical resection. *World J Surg Oncol* 18: 27.
4. Glatzer M, Rittmeyer A, Müller J, Opitz I, Papachristofilou A, et al. (2017) Treatment of limited disease small cell lung cancer: the multidisciplinary team. *Eur Respir J* 50: 1700422.
5. Glatzer M, Schmid S, Radovic M, Früh M, Putora PM (2017) The role of radiation therapy in the management of small cell lung cancer. *Breathe (Sheff)* 13: e87-e94.
6. Simone CB 2nd, Bogart JA, Cabrera AR, Daly ME, DeNunzio NJ, et al. (2020) Radiation Therapy for Small Cell Lung Cancer: An ASTRO Clinical Practice Guideline. *Pract Radiat Oncol* 10: 158-173.
7. Kruser TJ, McCabe BP, Mehta MP, Khuntia D, Campbell TC, et al. (2014) Reirradiation for locoregionally recurrent lung cancer: Outcomes in small cell and non-small cell lung carcinoma. *Am J Clin Oncol* 37: 70-76.
8. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2021) Omission of Radiation Therapy (RT) for Metaplastic Breast Cancer (MBC): A Review Article. *International Journal of Research Studies in Medical and Health Sciences* 6: 10-15.
9. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, et al. (2020) Multimodality management of cavernous sinus meningiomas with less extensive surgery followed by subsequent irradiation: Implications for an improved toxicity profile. *J Surg Surgical Res* 6: 56-61.
10. Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, et al. (2020) Single Fraction Stereotactic Radiosurgery (SRS) versus Fractionated Stereotactic Radiotherapy (FSRT) for Vestibular Schwannoma (VS). *J Surg Surgical Res* 6: 62-66.
11. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2020) Adaptive radiation therapy of breast cancer by repeated imaging during irradiation. *World J Radiol* 12: 68-75.
12. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, et al. (2020) A concise review of irradiation sequelae on the cardiovascular system in pulmonary malignancies. *J Surg Surgical Res* 6: 79-83.
13. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Demiral S, Dincoglan F, Gamsiz H, et al. (2020) Assessment of cardiac sparing in radiotherapeutic Management of mediastinal hodgkin lymphoma (hl) During childhood and adolescence. *J Surg Surgical Res* 6: 106-109.
14. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, et al. (2020) Obsessive compulsive disorder (ocd) as a severe mental health disorder: A concise review of management with radiosurgery for intractable disease. *J Surg Surgical Res* 6: 100-105.
15. Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Demiral S, Uysal B, et al. (2020) A Concise Review of Irradiation for Temporal Bone Chemodectomas (TBC). *Arch Otolaryngol Rhinol* 6: 16-20.
16. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, Uysal B, et al. (2019) Fractionated stereotactic radiosurgery for locally recurrent brain metastases after failed stereotactic radiosurgery. *Indian J Cancer* 56: 151-156.
17. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2019) Breathing adapted radiation therapy for leukemia relapse in the breast: A case report. *World J Clin Oncol* 10: 369-374.
18. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Uysal B, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, et al. (2019) Evaluation of hypofractionated stereotactic radiotherapy (HFSRT) to the resection cavity after surgical resection of brain metastases: A single center experience. *Indian J Cancer* 56: 202-206.
19. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2019) Utility of Molecular Imaging with 2-Deoxy-2-[Fluorine-18] Fluoro-DGlucose Positron Emission Tomography (18F-FDG PET) for Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC): A Radiation Oncology Perspective. *Curr Radiopharm* 12: 4-10.
20. Demiral S, Dincoglan F, Sager O, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2018) Contemporary Management of Meningiomas with Radiosurgery. *Int J Radiol Imaging Technol* 80: 187-190.
21. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Uysal B, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, et al. (2018) Evaluation of adaptive radiotherapy (ART) by use of replanning the tumor bed boost with repeated computed tomography (CT) simulation after whole breast irradiation (WBI) for breast cancer patients having clinically evident seroma. *Jpn J Radiol* 36: 401-406.
22. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Demiral S, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2017) Radiosurgery for recurrent glioblastoma: A review article. *Neurol Disord Therap* 1: 1-5.
23. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Uysal B, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, et al. (2017) Splenic Irradiation: A Concise Review of the Literature. *J App Hem BI Tran* 1: 101.
24. Demiral S, Dincoglan F, Sager O, Gamsiz H, Uysal B, et al. (2016) Hypofractionated stereotactic radiotherapy (HFSRT) for who grade I anterior clinoid meningiomas (ACM). *Jpn J Radiol* 34: 730-737.
25. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M (2015) Stereotactic radiosurgery of glomus jugulare tumors: Current concepts, recent advances and future perspectives. *CNS Oncol* 4: 105-114.
26. Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, et al. (2015) Management of patients with recurrent glioblastoma using hypofractionated stereotactic radiotherapy. *Tumori* 101: 179-184.
27. Gamsiz H, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Demiral S, Dincoglan F, et al. (2015) Evaluation of stereotactic body radiation therapy in the management of adrenal metastases from non-small cell lung cancer. *Tumori* 101: 98-103.

28. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, et al. (2015) Adaptive splenic radiotherapy for symptomatic splenomegaly management in myeloproliferative disorders. *Tumori* 101: 84-90.
29. Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Dincoglan F, Gamsiz H, et al. (2014) Evaluation of Linear Accelerator (Linac)-Based Stereotactic Radiosurgery (Srs) for the Treatment of Craniopharyngiomas. *UHOD- Int J Hematol Oncol* 24(2): 123-129.
30. Gamsiz H, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, et al. (2014) Management of pulmonary oligometastases by stereotactic body radiotherapy. *Tumori* 100: 179-183.
31. Ozsavaş EE, Telatar Z, Dirican B, Sager O, Beyzadeoğlu M (2014) Automatic segmentation of anatomical structures from CT scans of thorax for RTP. *Comput Math Methods Med* 2014: 472890.
32. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Gamsiz H, Demiral S, et al. (2014) Evaluation of linear accelerator-based stereotactic radiosurgery in the management of glomus jugulare tumors. *Tumori* 100: 184-188.
33. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2014) Evaluation of linear accelerator (LINAC)-based stereotactic radiosurgery (SRS) for cerebral cavernous malformations: A 15-year single-center experience. *Ann Saudi Med* 34: 54-58.
34. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Gamsiz H, Uysal B, Demiral S, et al. (2014) Management of patients with ≥ 4 brain metastases using stereotactic radiosurgery boost after whole brain irradiation. *Tumori* 100: 302-306.
35. Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Uysal B, Demiral S, et al. (2013) Evaluation of linear accelerator-based stereotactic radiosurgery in the management of meningiomas: A single center experience. *J BUON* 18: 717-722.
36. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Uysal B, et al. (2013) Management of vestibular schwannomas with linear accelerator-based stereotactic radiosurgery: a single center experience. *Tumori* 99: 617-622.
37. Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M, Uysal B, Oysul K, Kahya YE, et al. (2013) Evaluation of stereotactic body radiotherapy (SBRT) boost in the management of endometrial cancer. *Neoplasma* 60: 322-327.
38. Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Oysul K, Kahya YE, et al. (2013) Dosimetric evaluation of critical organs at risk in mastectomized left-sided breast cancer radiotherapy using breath-hold technique. *Tumori* 99: 76-82.
39. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Oysul K, Kahya YE, et al. (2012) The Role of Active Breathing Control-Moderate Deep Inspiration Breath-Hold (ABC-mDIBH) Usage in non-Mastectomized Left-sided Breast Cancer Radiotherapy: A Dosimetric Evaluation *UHOD - Int J Hematol Oncol* 22: 147-155.
40. Sağır Ö, Dinçoğlan F, Gamsiz H, Demiral S, Uysal B, et al. (2012) Evaluation of the impact of integrated [18f]-fluoro-2-deoxy-D-glucose positron emission tomography/computed tomography imaging on staging and radiotherapy treatment volume definition of nonsmall cell lung cancer. *Gulhane Med J* 54: 220-227.
41. Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Oysul K, Sirin S et al. (2012) Image-guided positioning in intracranial non-invasive stereotactic radiosurgery for the treatment of brain metastasis. *Tumori* 98: 630-635.
42. Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Oysul K, Kahya YE, et al. (2012) Evaluation of active breathing control-moderate deep inspiration breath-hold in definitive non-small cell lung cancer radiotherapy. *Neoplasma* 59: 333-340.
43. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Gamsiz H, Uysal B, Demiral S, et al. (2012) Stereotactic radiosurgery for intracranial tumors: A single center experience. *Gulhane Med J* 54: 190-198.
44. Sirin S, Oysul K, Surenkok S, Sager O, Dincoglan F, et al. (2011) Linear accelerator-based stereotactic radiosurgery in recurrent glioblastoma: A single center experience. *Vojnosanit Pregl* 68: 961-966.
45. Tjong MC, Mak DY, Shahi J, Li GJ, Chen H, et al. (2020) Current Management and Progress in Radiotherapy for Small Cell Lung Cancer. *Front Oncol* 10: 1146.
46. Cai S, Shi A, Yu R, Zhu G (2014) Feasibility of omitting clinical target volume for limited-disease small cell lung cancer treated with chemotherapy and intensity-modulated radiotherapy. *Radiat Oncol* 9: 17.
47. Levy A, Faivre-Finn C (2020) Radiotherapy tumor volume for limited-stage small cell lung cancer: less is more. *Ann Transl Med* 8: 1114.
48. Le Pechoux C, Faivre-Finn C, Ramella S, McDonald F, Manapov F, et al. (2020) ESTRO ACROP guidelines for target volume definition in the thoracic radiation treatment of small cell lung cancer. *Radiother Oncol* 152: 89-95.
49. Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M (2021) Evaluation of Target Definition for Management of Myxoid Liposarcoma (MLS) with Neoadjuvant Radiation Therapy (RT). *Biomed J Sci & Tech Res* 33: 26171-26174.
50. Demiral S, Dincoglan F, Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M (2021) Multimodality Imaging Based Target Definition of Cervical Lymph Nodes in Precise Limited Field Radiation Therapy (Lfrt) for Nodular Lymphocyte Predominant Hodgkin Lymphoma (Nlphl). *ARC Journal of Cancer Science* 6: 6-11.
51. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2021) Target Definition of orbital Embryonal Rhabdomyosarcoma (Rms) by Multimodality Imaging: An Original Article. *ARC Journal of Cancer Science* 6: 12-17.
52. Sager O, Demiral S, Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M (2020) Target Volume Definition for Stereotactic Radiosurgery (SRS) Of

- Cerebral Cavernous Malformations (CCMs). *Canc Therapy & Oncol Int J* 15: 555917.
53. Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M, Demiral S, Sager O (2020) Assessment of Treatment Volume Definition for Irradiation of Spinal Ependymomas: an Original Article. *ARC Journal of Cancer Science* 6: 1-6.
 54. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2020) Radiosurgery Treatment Volume Determination for Brain Lymphomas with and without Incorporation of Multimodality Imaging. *J med Pharm Allied Sci* 9: 2398-2404.
 55. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2020) Assessment of Target Volume Definition for Irradiation of Hemangiopericytomas: An Original Article. *Canc Therapy & Oncol Int J* 17(2).
 56. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2020) Evaluation of Treatment Volume Determination for Irradiation of chordoma: an Original Article. *International Journal of Research Studies in Medical and Health Sciences* 5 (10): 3-8
 57. Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Sager O, Beyzadeoglu M (2020) Utility of Multimodality Imaging Based Target Volume Definition for Radiosurgery of Trigeminal Neuralgia: An Original Article. *Biomed J Sci & Tech Res* 26: 19728-19732.
 58. Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Sager O (2020) Target Volume Determination for Precise Radiation Therapy (RT) of Central Neurocytoma: An Original Article. *International Journal of Research Studies in Medical and Health Sciences* 5: 29-34.
 59. Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Sager O, Demiral S (2020) Determination of Radiosurgery Treatment Volume for Intracranial Germ Cell Tumors (GCTS). *Asian Journal of Pharmacy, Nursing and Medical Sciences* 8: 18-23.
 60. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2020) Evaluation of Target Volume Determination for Irradiation of Pilocytic Astrocytomas: An Original Article. *ARC Journal of Cancer Science* 6: 1-5.
 61. Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Sager O (2020) Assessment of Target Volume Definition for Radiosurgery of Atypical Meningiomas with Multimodality Imaging. *J. Hematol. Oncol. Res* 3: 14-21.
 62. Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M, Dincoglan F, Sager O (2020) Evaluation of Radiosurgery Target Volume Definition for Tectal Gliomas with Incorporation of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI): An Original Article. *Biomed J Sci & Tech Res (BJSTR)* 27: 20543-20547.
 63. Demiral S, Sager O, Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M (2019) Assessment of Computed Tomography (CT) And Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) Based Radiosurgery Treatment Planning for Pituitary Adenomas. *Canc Therapy & Oncol Int J* 13: 555857.
 64. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, Uysal B, et al. (2019) Evaluation of the Impact of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) on Gross Tumor Volume (GTV) Definition for Radiation Treatment Planning (RTP) of Inoperable High Grade Gliomas (HGGs). *Concepts in Magnetic Resonance Part A* 2019, Article ID 4282754.
 65. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2019) Incorporation of Multimodality Imaging in Radiosurgery Planning for Craniopharyngiomas: An Original Article. *SAJ Cancer Sci* 6: 103.
 66. Dincoglan F, Sager O, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2019) Multimodality Imaging for Radiosurgical Management of Arteriovenous Malformations. *Asian Journal of Pharmacy, Nursing and Medical Sciences* 7: 7-12.
 67. Demiral S, Sager O, Dincoglan F, Beyzadeoglu M (2019) Assessment of target definition based on Multimodality imaging for radiosurgical Management of glomus jugulare tumors (GJTs). *Canc Therapy & Oncol Int J* 15: 555909.
 68. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Gamsiz H, Uysal B, et al. (2019) Utility of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (Imaging) in Target Volume Definition for Radiosurgery of Acoustic Neuromas. *Int J Cancer Clin Res* 6: 119.
 69. Beyzadeoglu M, Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S (2019) Evaluation of Target Definition for Stereotactic Reirradiation of Recurrent Glioblastoma. *Arch Can Res* 7: 3.
 70. Sager O, Dincoglan F, Demiral S, Beyzadeoglu M (2019) Evaluation of Radiosurgery Target Volume Determination for Meningiomas Based on Computed Tomography (CT) And Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). *Cancer Sci Res Open Access* 5: 1-4.
 71. Demiral S, Sager O, Dincoglan F, Uysal B, Gamsiz H, et al. (2018) Evaluation of Target Volume Determination for Single Session Stereotactic Radiosurgery (SRS) of Brain Metastases. *Canc Therapy & Oncol Int J* 12: 555848.